

Water-smartness dashboard – Final release

Deliverable 3.7

Water-smartness dashboard- Final release

B-WaterSmart dashboard – Document accompanying the tool

Summary

The B-WaterSmart dashboard is a web application, which utilizes the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework (detailed in Deliverable D6.3) to aid decision-makers in the water sector with strategic planning, aiming to evaluate progress towards a water-smart society. Within the B-WaterSmart project, Living Labs, including water utilities and municipalities, used the dashboard as a management support tool under the Innovation Alliance (T1.4) and provided feedback, contributing to improvements within its final version. In its current final release (due in August 2024), apart from the main functionalities mentioned in the early version (described in detail in D3.6), there's the possibility of the following: a) to disaggregate metrics, b) to associate different weights for each metrics, c) to assign accuracy to interview-based metrics and visualize the result, d) to copy an assessment, e) to set metrics as 'context', f) to adjust the reference values, g) to establish targets h) to compare different alternatives i) to export the data in smart data model in Fiware format.

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Dissemination level

- PU = Public**
- PP = Restricted to other programme participants
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- CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium

D1.6 Final portfolio of training actions

History of changes

Version	Date	Changes and comments
1.0	30/08/24	Submission on time.
2.0	05/12/24	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Following the reviewer's suggestion, the executive summary was removed.• Introduction was revised regarding the objectives of the framework, the targeted audiences, and the expected results (section 1).• Indications on how the next steps indicated in D3.6 were delivered were added (section 2).• The description of the dashboard and its functionalities was reviewed, and new screenshots were included (section 3).• General revisions to improve reader-friendliness.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AC	Assessment Criteria
AF	Assessment Framework
BWS	B-WaterSmart
Dx.y	Deliverable y of WPx
InAll	Innovation Alliance
LL	Living Labs
SO	Strategic Objective
Tx.y	Task y of WPx
WPx	Work Package x
UI	User Interface
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSG	Static Site Generation
SSR	Server-Side Reading

1 Introduction

This report together with the tool available at <https://bws-dashboard.iccs.gr/> constitutes the B-WaterSmart project's *Deliverable 3.7 B-WaterSmart dashboard – Final release*. D3.7, developed from T3.9, involves the development of an online dashboard, which implements the B-WaterSmart assessment framework created in WP6 and the step-by-step strategic planning process from T1.4 (WP1). The objectives of the framework can be briefly summarized as: 1) to support strategic planning, 2) to enable overcoming barriers in implementation of strategic agendas for water smart societies and 3) to facilitate benchmarking by delivering a set of metrics accompanied by reference values. The objectives are explained in detail in Deliverable 6.3 (Silva et al. 2023). The document should be referred to for any further clarifications in relation to the framework, as it contains explanations of the terms used in the dashboard and in D3.7. An attempt was made for the dashboard to support the framework objectives and as a result, to provide a useful tool facilitating the use of the framework and implementation of strategic planning.

This report is provided for the convenience of current and future potential users of the dashboard, detailing the final version and main functionalities of the tool. The target audience of the deliverable and targeted users of the tool include the BWS consortium, B-WaterSmart Living Labs, InAll partners (BWS Innovation Alliance described in Rebelo et al., 2021), regional decision-makers, European and national authorities, researchers, and consultants. As a public deliverable, anyone interested can register and use the tool.

The document presents the final overview of all functionalities for facilitating the understanding of the tool, its architecture, and its possible applications beyond the project. More details can be found in D3.6 (Lekawska-Andrinopoulou et al. 2023).

2 Methodology

The detailed methodology is described in D3.6, and the information in this section complement the information provided. As indicated in the next steps section of the D3.6, during the period from the submission of D3.6 (August 2023), corresponding to the early version of the dashboard, until delivering the final version of the tool (August 2024) the ICCS team continued to cooperate with teams of SINTEF and LNEC in terms of conceptualization of the tool, whenever such need arose. As a result of those discussions and as InAll proceeded with using the tool, the list of recommendations for improvement from D1.3 (Cardoso et al., 2022) was updated together with functionalities to be added as described in D3.6. As a result, some of the functionalities were defined as of “low priority”, while other functionalities were added to the list. The final list of functionalities is also available in Appendix A of D3.7.

The discussion with SINTEF and LNEC teams has also resulted in modifications of the draft mockups presented in D3.6, to make sure the UI matches better the expectations. Additionally, following the advice of WP1 leaders, a 3-week period (during May/June 2024) was assigned for testing by the users and feedback collection, putting on hold some of the development and creating a need to prioritize the functionalities of more value for the users.

Finally, the dashboard is developed based on the Nextjs platform, comprising a functionality for the users to enter data regarding the various assessments and a functionality to visualize results and data insights. The system follows a client server architecture using RPC (Remote Process Calls). These calls provide the capability for data exchange and reliable processing at the backend that includes the calculation of normalization vectors for various metrics, criteria, and overall assessments. We present the main API calls in the Appendix B.

In D3.6 next steps towards the development of the final version of the tool (Section 4) were presented in terms of dashboard use in BWS (Section 4.1) and the development (Section 4.2).

3 Dashboard – final version

The BWS dashboard implements digitally the B-WaterSmart Assessment Framework (BWS AF) to support the strategic planning process for achieving the water-smartness described in BWS deliverable (Silva et al., 2023). In the final version of the tool, all the required steps of the strategic planning process are implemented, namely Step 1 – Selection of strategic objectives, assessment criteria, metrics and reference values, Step 2 – Diagnosis, including scenarios creation, Step 3 - Set the targets, Step 4 – Develop the strategic plan, Step 5 - Implement the strategic plan, Step 6 - Monitor performance. Table 1 presents the main functionalities following the flow, a user would take to complete an assessment. A comprehensive list of generic functionalities available in the dashboard is also listed in Appendix A.

The final version of the dashboard tool, available at <https://bws-dashboard.iccs.gr/>, is accessible by using the following credentials:

- Username: iccs
- Password: iccsBWS

Table 1. B-WaterSmart Dashboard main functionalities are illustrated together with relevant screenshots from the tool. The functionalities are described per step of strategic planning.

Functionality and short description	
General	
1	Sign in: The dashboard sign in page was presented in Deliverable 3.6
2	<p>Draft Assessments page incl. possibility of copying assessment: User can see ongoing assessments and the last step, that was completed per assessment. In this view user can rename, make a copy or delete an assessment.</p>
3	Creating new assessment: User chooses “New Assessment”, needs to give it a title and optionally provides a description. The functionality is described in detail in D3.6. It is shown in D3.7 for integrity of user flow.

4 **Accessing previous assessment:** Presented in D3.6

Functionalities relevant to STEP 1

5 **Selection of SO, AC and metrics.** Functionality reflects **Strategic planning Step 1: user chooses strategic objectives, assessment criteria and metrics.** This functionality is described in detail in D3.6. It is shown in D3.7 for integrity of user flow.

D3.7

Strategic Objectives
 Assessment criteria
 3 Metrics

Select the metrics per selected assessment criterion, you would like to include in the assessment.

Selected assessment criteria	4 metric available
B.3 Resource efficiency	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metric "E.3.1" Stakeholders inclusiveness CORE
C.3 Resource recovery and efficient use	<input type="checkbox"/> Metric "E.3.2" Protection of core values CORE
E.3 Stakeholder engagement processes	<input type="checkbox"/> Metric "E.3.3" Cross-stakeholders learning CORE
	<input type="checkbox"/> Metric "E.3.4" Collaborative agents CORE

6 **Inputting the values:** User provides input values to calculate each metric. The functionality is described in detail in D3.6. It is shown in D3.7 for integrity of the user flow.

Strategic Objectives
 Assessment criteria
 Metrics

Select each metric and add input and/or output values.

Inputs

B. Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society > B.1 Safeguarded water ecosystems > **Metric "B.1.2" Effective stormwater treatment**

Equation

$$SWT_{eff} = \frac{A_{Treatment}}{A_{Total}} \times 100$$

Set as 'Context metric'
 Context metrics are not included in the calculations.

Please fill the option(s) below.

m²
 m²
 %

Reference values

7 **Include the default reference values in the dashboard, and the possibility to adjust them.** User has the option to adjust reference values or to use the default ones.

Reference Values

Set your own reference values for this metric.

[Reset Values](#)

8

Possibility to disaggregate metrics. At the metric screen, user can disaggregate metric as appropriated and needed.

Select each metric and add input and/or output values.

Inputs

B. Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society > > **Metric "B.1.2" Effective stormwater treatment**

Equation

$$SWT_{eff} = \frac{A_{Treatment}}{A_{Total}} \times 100$$

Please fill the option(s) below.

m²
 m²
 %

Reference values

9. Possibility of setting a metric as 'context metric'. User can set metric as “context”. Those metrics support interpretation of results and will not be used for visualization, not included in aggregation to SO, AC, not considered for targets setting, alternatives, etc.

B. Safeguarding ecosystems and their services to society > B.1 Safeguarded water ecosystems> **Metric "B.1.2" Effective stormwater treatment**

Equation

$$SWT_{eff} = \frac{A_{Treatment}}{A_{Total}} \times 100$$

Please fill the option(s) below.

m²
 m²
 %

Set as 'Context metric'

Context metrics are not included in the calculations.

Context metrics describe pure context and external factors that cannot be assessed by one specific user.

10 **Possibility of assigning accuracy to interview-based metrics.** For the interview-based metrics, an option for assigning accuracy (more assessment is necessary, sufficiently confident, confident) appears automatically.

Strategic Objectives Assessment criteria Metrics

Select each metric and add input and/or output values.

Inputs

E. Engaging citizens and actors across sectors in continuous co-learning and innovation > E.3 Stakeholder engagement processes > **Metric 'E.3.1' Stakeholders inclusiveness**

Interview

Don't forget!
 Read the interview guide before performing interviews.
 Improved Interview Guide

Output (Score)

Select one.

Functionalities relevant to STEP 2

11 **Visualization of the results for different SO: Functionality reflects together with scenarios setting Strategic planning Step 2: Diagnosis** and is described in detail in D3.6. It is shown in D3.7 for integrity of user flow.

12 **Visualization of accuracy:** User can see the accuracy levels assigned at earlier stage to each interview-based metric gathered in one graph.

13 **Possibility to associate different weights for each metric:** User has the possibility to associate different weights for each assessment criterion choosing between low, medium or high, with medium being the default.

Assessment Criteria	Weight		
	Low	Medium	High
E.3 Stakeholder engagement processes			
B.3 Resource efficiency			
C.3 Resource recovery and efficient use			
B.1 Safeguarded water ecosystems			
<input type="button" value="Cancel"/>		<input type="button" value="Save changes"/>	

14 **Scenarios creation:** Functionality reflects **Strategic planning Step 2: Diagnosis (analysis of scenarios)** and is described in detail in D3.6. It is shown in D3.7 for integrity of the user flow.

Initial assessment	External context changes expected	Expected trend	Expected performance level (with no investments)
<p>Metric "E.3.1" Stakeholders inclusiveness</p>	<p><input type="button" value="Yes"/> <input type="button" value="No"/></p> <p><input type="text" value="Short description"/></p>	<p></p>	<p><input type="button" value="Good"/> <input type="button" value="Fair"/> <input type="button" value="Poor"/></p>
<p>Metric "B.1.2" Effective stormwater treatment</p>	<p><input type="button" value="Yes"/> <input type="button" value="No"/></p> <p><input type="text" value="Short description"/></p>	<p></p>	<p><input type="button" value="Good"/> <input type="button" value="Fair"/> <input type="button" value="Poor"/></p>
<p>Metric "B.3.1" Water Footprint</p>	<p><input type="button" value="Yes"/> <input type="button" value="No"/></p> <p><input type="text" value="Short description"/></p>	<p></p>	<p><input type="button" value="Good"/> <input type="button" value="Fair"/> <input type="button" value="Poor"/></p>

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Functionalities relevant to STEP 3

15 **Possibility to establish targets:** Functionality reflects **Strategic planning Step 3: Set the targets**. User can set short/medium/long term targets for each metric. Each term can be defined by the user by choosing a relevant year.

Initial assessment (Now)	Short-term 2027	Medium-term 2031	Long-term 2035
<p>Metric "E.3.1" Stakeholders inclusiveness</p>	<p>Target Value: <input type="text" value="100"/> ● Good</p> <p>Milestones: <input type="text" value="MS1 ..."/></p>	<p>Target Value: <input type="text" value="100"/> ● Good</p> <p>Milestones: <input type="text" value="MS2 ..."/></p>	<p>Target Value: <input type="text" value="100"/> ● Good</p> <p>Milestones: <input type="text"/></p>
<p>Metric "B.1.2" Effective stormwater treatment</p>	<p>Target Value: <input type="text" value="2"/></p> <p>Milestones: <input type="text"/></p>	<p>Target Value: <input type="text" value="1"/></p> <p>Milestones: <input type="text"/></p>	<p>Target Value: <input type="text" value="1"/></p> <p>Milestones: <input type="text"/></p>
<p>Metric "B.3.1" Water Footprint</p>	<p>Target Value: <input type="text"/></p> <p>Milestones: <input type="text"/></p>	<p>Target Value: <input type="text"/></p> <p>Milestones: <input type="text"/></p>	<p>Target Value: <input type="text"/></p> <p>Milestones: <input type="text"/></p>

Functionalities relevant to STEP 4

16 **Setting up alternatives:** Functionality reflects **Strategic planning Step 4: Develop strategic plan**. User can describe each alternative.

Alternative 1: D3.7 Alternative A

Add a title for your alternative and describe the factors that will influence the analysis.

1 ————— 2 ————— 3

Title & description Select metrics Select time horizon

Title *
Give your alternative a title

Description
Describe the factor(s) that will influence the analysis.

Your description

17 **Metric selection for alternative:** Functionality reflects **Strategic planning Step 4: Develop strategic plan**. User can select the relevant metrics to assess each alternative.

Alternative 1: D3.7 Alternative A

Select the metrics you would like to include in this alternative solutions.

Metrics selected for initial assessment

- ✓ Metric "B.1.2" Effective stormwater treatment **CORE**
- ✓ Metric "B.3.1" Water Footprint **CORE**
- Metric "C.3.2" Fertilizer production avoided **CORE**
- ✓ Metric "E.3.1" Stakeholders inclusiveness **CORE**
- ✓ Metric "E.3.2" Protection of core values **CORE**
- ✓ Metric "E.3.3" Cross-stakeholders learning **CORE**
- Metric "E.3.4" Collaborative agents **CORE**

18 **Selection of time horizon.** Functionality reflects [Strategic planning Step 4: Develop strategic plan](#). User can select the time horizon for analysis for alternative and metric values per time horizon.

Alternative 1: D3.7 Alternative A

Select the time horizons you would like to include in this alternative.

Time Horizons
Select up to 3

2024 × 2027 × 2029 ×

19 **Metric values for the alternatives.** Functionality reflects [Strategic planning Step 4: Develop strategic plan](#). User provides the metric values for time horizon and alternative, allowing prospective evaluation.

20 **Comparison of different alternatives.** Functionality reflects **Strategic planning Step 4: Develop strategic plan.** User can visualize the performance of each alternative along the time horizon analysed.

21 **Result summary page.** Functionality reflects **Strategic planning Step 4: Develop strategic plan.**, summarizes the results in one screen.

22 Export to pdf: The results of Summary page can be exported to pdf

Export to PDF

Strategic plan

Summary of the diagnosis and of the selected alternative solutions.

Assessment selections

Strategic planning STEP 5: Implement the strategic plan is performed outside of the dashboard environment

Functionalities relevant to STEP 6

23 **Performance monitoring:** Functionality reflects Strategic planning Step 6: Performance monitoring and allows the user to assess performance after implementation of the strategic plan, gives a visualization on how far the user's targets have been met, what is on track and achieved earlier or what is behind track.

Targets VS Achieved values			
Metric - Initial assessment value	Short-term 2024	Medium-term 2028	Long-term 2032
Metric "E.3.1" Stakeholders inclusiveness 	3.1	3.1	4.9
Metric "B.1.2" Effective stormwater treatment 	100 ● Good	100 ● Good	100 ● Good
Metric "B.3.1" Water Footprint 	2 ● Poor	2 ● Poor	1 ● Good
Metric "C.3.2" Fertilizer production avoided 	60 ● Good	60 ● Good	70 ● Good

The Export Function in smart data model (Fiware format) is a function where the assessment related data is stored in both relational database and Fiware and can be exported through the queries or supported Fiware API calls. The Fiware API call is based on the Stelio context broker which is installed within the BWS dashboard backend system.

4 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the final version of the B-WaterSmart dashboard developed under the B-WaterSmart project. In the final version of the tool, all the required steps of the strategic planning process are implemented and D3.7 presents the main functionalities following the flow a user would take to complete an assessment. D3.7 complements the D3.6, which should be referred for full methodology and other aspects, when needed.

Disclaimer of Warranties

This project has used a standard methodology already developed in B-Water Smart project (Grant Agreement number: 869171) and AWARE-P project (<http://aware-p.org/np4/presentation/>), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for B-Water Smart project (Grant Agreement number: 869171).

The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the following information.

5 References

Cardoso, M.A., et al. (2022) Recommendations for refinement of the water-smartness framework and its transformation into a dashboard-type software, H2020 B-WaterSmart Deliverable D1.3 <https://b-watersmart.eu//results-downloads/water-smartness-assessment-framework/#> (last accessed 7/8/2024)

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Silva, C., et al. (2023). Final version of the water-smartness assessment framework (V2), H2020 B-WaterSmart Deliverable 6.3. <https://b-watersmart.eu/download/final-version-of-the-water-smartness-assessment-framework-pdf-deliverable-6-3/> (last accessed 31/7/2024)

Appendix A. Final list of the functionalities available in the dashboard in reference to recommendations presented in D1.3 and extra functionalities

Recommendation from D1.3	Status in dashboard final release
The name of the metric to be included in the selection panel	Available
Visualization of the results for different SO	Available
Visualization of the judgement of each metric based on the reference values (good, fair, and poor performance)	Available
Metric normalization based on the defined judgement	Available
Prospective evaluation for different scenarios	Available
Visualization of the strategic assessment on a temporal basis (through metric computation for different years)	Available
Possibility to disaggregate metrics	Available
Include the default reference values in the dashboard, and the possibility to adjust them	Available
The possibility to associate different weights for each metric	Available
The possibility to establish targets	Available
Comparison of different alternatives	Available
The normalization of metric's results	Available
Automatically import to the dashboard the input values	Functionality not prioritized
Include possibility to define other metrics	Functionality withdrawn due to risk related to significant changes in the framework by not experienced user
Identify the input variables needed; for each input variable identify the selected metrics it is used for	Functionality not prioritized, low impact
Allow to visualize the results from different points of view/dimensions: social, environmental, economic, technical, governance	Functionality not prioritized, low impact
Extra functionalities	
Assigning accuracy to interview based metrics and visualization	Available
Possibility of copying assessment	Available

The possibility to set metric as “context”	Available
Export Function in smart data model (Firmware format)	Available

Appendix B. List of API Calls

getAssessment

- Method: Query
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)
- Description: Retrieves a detailed assessment including its strategic objectives, criteria, metrics, and other related data if the user has permission.

· **copyAssessment**

- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)
- Description: Creates a copy of an existing assessment, duplicating its strategic objectives, criteria, metrics, and other related data.

· **createSkeleton**

- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentTitle (string), assessmentDesc (string)
- Description: Creates a new assessment skeleton with basic details such as title and description.

· **updateTitleDesc**

- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), assessmentTitle (string, optional), assessmentDesc (string, optional)
- Description: Updates the title and/or description of an assessment if the user has permission.

· **updateStage**

- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), stage (string)
- Description: Updates the stage of an assessment if the user has permission.

· **isDiagnosisCalculated**

- Method: Query
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)

- Description: Checks if the diagnosis for an assessment has been calculated.
- **calculateDiagnosis**
- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)
- Description: Calculates the diagnosis for an assessment by processing its metrics and criteria.
- **updateStrategicObjectives**
- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), strategicObjectives (array of numbers)
- Description: Updates the strategic objectives of an assessment, adding new ones and removing those no longer needed.
- **updateAssessmentCriteria**
- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), assessmentCriteria (array of numbers)
- Description: Updates the assessment criteria, adding new ones and removing those no longer needed.
- **updateMetrics**
- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), metrics (array of numbers)
- Description: Updates the metrics of an assessment, adding new ones and removing those no longer needed.
- **updateInputs**
- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), inputs (array of numbers, optional), inputValues, outputValues, interviewValues, interviewAccuracies, questionnaireValues, selectedReferenceValues (all records of numbers or strings)
- Description: Updates the inputs and their values for an assessment, including handling equations and references.
- **updateMetricWeights**
- Method: Mutation

- Input: assessmentId (number), metricWeights (record of numbers)
- Description: Updates the weights of metrics for an assessment.
- **updateMetricsCore**
- Method: Mutation
- Input: assessmentId (number), metricId (number), isCore (boolean)
- Description: Toggles the 'isCore' status of a metric in an assessment.
- **updateAccWeights**
- Method: Mutation
- Input: assessmentId (number), accWeights (record of numbers)
- Description: Updates the weights of assessment criteria.
- **updateDisaggregatedSet**
- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), disaggregatedInputSets (array of objects with inputId and value)
- Description: Updates disaggregated input sets for an assessment.
- **deleteAssessment**
- Method: Mutation
- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)
- Description: Deletes an assessment if the user has permission.
- **getAssessmentStages**
- Method: Query
- Input: None
- Description: Retrieves the stages of the assessment process from the navigation bar items.
- **getEquation**
- Method: Query
- Input: equationId (number)
- Description: Retrieves an equation by its ID, including its inputs, outputs, and reference values.

- **getGlobalEquation**

- Method: Query

- Input: globalEquationId (number)

- Description: Retrieves a global equation by its ID, including its inputs and related details.

- **getUnit**

- Method: Query

- Input: unitId (number)

- Description: Retrieves a unit by its ID.

- **getStages**

- Method: Query

- Input: navBarItemId (number)

- Description: Retrieves the sub-navigation items (stages) for a given navigation bar item ID.

- **getAllAssessments**

- Method: Query

- Input: None

- Description: Retrieves all assessments, including their strategic objectives, criteria, metrics, inputs, and input values.

- **deleteAssessment (Updated)**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)

- Description: Deletes an assessment if the user has permission and matches the user ID associated with the assessment.

API calls related to alternatives:

- **createDraftAlternative**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)

- Description: Creates a draft alternative for a specified user and assessment.

- **updatePrimaryAlternative**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), alternativeId (number)

- Description: Updates the primary alternative for a specified assessment.

- **createOrUpdateAlternative**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), alternativeId (number, optional), alternativeTitle (string, optional), alternativeDescription (string, optional),

- timeHorizon1 (number, optional), timeHorizon2 (number, optional), timeHorizon3 (number, optional), selectedMetricsIds (array of numbers, optional), alternativeValues (record of objects, optional)

- Description: Creates or updates an alternative with the specified details.

- **deleteAlternative**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), alternativeId (number)

- Description: Deletes a specified alternative if the user has the necessary permissions.

- **getMetricsByIds**

- Method: Query

- Input: metricIds (array of numbers)

- Description: Retrieves metrics with the specified IDs, including their associated output.

The following API calls are related to performance monitoring:

- **createDraftPerformanceMonitoring**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), availableYears (array of numbers)

- Description: Creates a draft performance monitoring entry for a specified user and assessment or returns the existing draft if one already exists.

- **createOrUpdatePerformanceMonitoring**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), performanceMonitoringId (number), year (number), items (record of numbers)

- Description: Creates or updates a performance monitoring entry for a specified year and updates its items, setting the draft status to false.

- **deletePerformanceMonitoring**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)

- Description: Deletes a performance monitoring entry for a specified user and assessment if the user has permission.

- **getPerformanceMonitoring**

- Method: Query

- Input: userId (string), performanceMonitoringId (number)

- Description: Retrieves a performance monitoring entry along with its items if the user has permission. Converts availableYears from string to array.

- **getAllPerformanceMonitorings**

- Method: Query

- Input: None

- Description: Retrieves all performance monitoring entries, including their metrics, values, and related data.

- **deletePerformanceMonitoring**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)

- Description: Deletes a performance monitoring entry if the user has permission and matches the user ID associated with the entry.

The following API calls are related to the management of scenarios:

- **createDraftScenario**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number)

- Description: Creates a draft scenario for a specified user and assessment.

- **createOrUpdateScenario**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), scenarioId (number), scenarioTitle (string, optional), scenarioDescription (string, optional), yesNoValues (record of objects with value and description, optional), trends (record of strings, optional), performanceValues (record of strings, optional)

- Description: Creates or updates a scenario, deleting existing values and inserting new ones based on the input.

- **deleteScenario**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), scenarioId (number)

- Description: Deletes a scenario if the user has permission.

- **getMetricById**

- Method: Query

- Input: id (number)

- Description: Retrieves a metric by its ID, including its outputs, global equation inputs, and reference values.

- **getAllScenarios**

- Method: Query

- Input: None

- Description: Retrieves all scenarios, including their metrics, values, and related data.

- **deleteScenario (Updated)**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), scenarioId (number)

- Description: Deletes a scenario if the user has permission and matches the user ID associated with the scenario.

The following API calls are related to the management of targets:

- **createDraftTarget**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), assessmentId (number), shortTermYear (number), mediumTermYear (number), longTermYear (number)

- Description: Creates a draft target for a specified user and assessment or returns the existing draft if one already exists.

- **createOrUpdateTarget**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), targetId (number), targetItems (array of objects with metricId, shortTermValue, shortTermMilestones, mediumTermValue, mediumTermMilestones, longTermValue, longTermMilestones), shortTermYear (number), mediumTermYear (number), longTermYear (number)

- Description: Creates or updates a target, deleting existing target items and inserting new ones based on the input.

- **deleteTarget**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), targetId (number)

- Description: Deletes a target if the user has permission.

- **getAllTargets**

- Method: Query

- Input: None

- Description: Retrieves all targets, including their metrics, values, and related data.

- **deleteTarget (Updated)**

- Method: Mutation

- Input: userId (string), targetId (number)

- Description: Deletes a target if the user has permission and matches the user ID associated with the target.

The following api calls provide the functionality to extract BWS questionnaire data from the FIWARE persistence layer.

- **-uploadEntity**

- **Method:** Http Post
- **Input:** Http body
- **Description:** uploads a Fiware entity to the BWS Stellio components

-getEntity

- **Method:** Http Get
- **Input:** Path parameters by entity ID or type
- **Description:** Reads BWS entity and its associated parameters

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